

A Third World Modern Urbanism

I am grateful for having been so kindly invited by the organizers of this meeting, through the person of Frederico Holanda, to be present here today.

I must say that I rise to this podium with great and justifiable fear. It is very difficult, first of all, when one endeavors to be an epistemologist, to speak in a way that might immediately or mechanically interest epistemologists of other areas and, secondly, to speak of things one truly believes in to an international audience, since concepts are rarely capable of crossing borders. There is a border between geography — or, rather, geographers — and urbanists, which constitutes a challenge when trying to bring forth something that might be of interest. Perhaps that border to be traversed together is the city itself. Or, more than the city, the urban.

What I have been asked to do may at first sight seem like futurology. In fact, it is much less than that and much more than that, since what I have been asked to talk about here is the future. And the end of the 20th century finally allows us to treat utopias in a scientific manner — that old dream of thinkers and scientists — in so far as this end of the century appears to be a great life jacket for thinkers, since for the first time in the history of Man we have before us the idea and the fact of empirical universality. That is, it is the first time in the history of Man, and therefore in the history of thought, that the world reveals itself everywhere in the plenitude of things known (or not), of ideas known (or not), of relationships known (or not), as a system of empirical data, part of which is used here and there to build the so-called concrete history, while the rest remains outside of it, yet ready to be used as true, concrete, empirical facts in the creation of a new concrete history. Thus the discussion of the future becomes possible. Thus the idea of utopia can no longer be called pointless. Thus it becomes our duty to be utopian

above all, since the job of the intellectual is only truly worthwhile when it focuses, first of all, on the interest of the majority, and, secondly, on the possible future.

What might this urban future be? What might be the concrete possibility of bringing forth the new that has not yet become? How can we mentally gather the elements that have been taken from the existing reality, or the reality to become; the materials that will make that future reality? I start by recalling Jean Jacques Rousseau's words when, referring to the cities, he said, "The city is not the things. The city is the things plus the people." The city is, above all, a live work that in the end becomes a universal work built on dead work, which also appears to be universal. Dead work that acquires significance and value through live work). Live work that permits the intellectual operations necessary to turn the dead thing — the landscape — socially significant through the life injected to it by man's actions. Those human actions that provide intelligibility to technique, because technique is not intelligible by itself. In fact, technique does not exist by itself. It only acquires historical existence through human action. And this end of the century shows us, more than other centuries and millenniums could have shown us, that history revolves around two poles: technique and politics. I say this precisely in order to be able to talk to urbanists, who are the men and women that work with things and who believe that things can command politics, when, if we want things to have social significance, we must conceive them as being produced by politics, as acquiring significance through politics, as being prone to change through politics. I believe this discussion is necessary for all of those who work with space, but it is above all indispensable for urbanists, those men of space that work much more with things than they do with actions in their transience, because they apparently work with ready-made actions and they believe that these dead actions can have an effect on life.

In order to continue the argument, it is necessary to discuss, however briefly — and I apologize for doing so, since I imagine that all of this is well known, if only to point out some of the traits that underlie everything I will say, and therefore will not be repeated in the following pages — some of what in essence characterizes today these two pillars of the history of Man: technique and politics.

Technique, the technical system that surrounds us and that somehow constitutes the framework of our lives, is highly scientific, highly artificial, highly intentional, strongly systemic and invasive. And politics, which rules our lives, decides the way in which technique imposes our destiny upon us. Politics, which is today characterized by being as technical

and scientific as technique, tends nonetheless to be privatizing, anti-republican, anti-citizen — and it is important to discuss this when talking about urbanism and *urbis* —, and tends to be controlled by businesses, so much so that in some states, especially those of poor or politically impoverished countries, businesses govern more than governments.

The result of the conjunction of these two factors is that large cities — especially the large cities of today — have finally become the concrete realization of that which in the 70s was called capitalist socialization. Without this capitalist socialization it is impossible to understand either urbanism or the work of urbanists in relation to cities and citizens. This capitalist socialization can be measured through some data of which I will speak briefly. The first is the appetite for competitiveness exhibited by large businesses. Competitiveness, as everyone knows, is competition exercised without compassion. And this competitiveness is creative. It imposes the need to create potential fluidity, which by the way is one of the guiding lights of contemporary urbanism and may be more so in the urbanism of the future, if the current political system continues. This potential fluidity, which is one of the most remarkable aspects of today's world and reflects directly upon the city and the urban — it is the creation of potential fluidity that allows businesses to become more fluid in the urban space and in space in general —, leads to the need to expand the new, to exacerbate the new. But now, thanks to the virtualities of the technical system, of a new that is hypertelic, in other words, a new that is created with a plethora of intentionality, an intentionality that is adapted to the necessities of fluidity of these same large businesses — less and less numerous among the ensemble of businesses, more and more dominant in the national and international urban scene, with extremely large and grave repercussions on urban life, especially urban reconstructions, in sum, on current urbanism, especially in underdeveloped regions. And this is the consequence. The so-called renewal results precisely in the premature aging of the city, because by renovating a part of the city — based on a hypertelic urbanistic perspective, that is, an urbanistic perspective plethoric with intentionality —, I am at the same time aging the rest of the city. And the rest of the city, which is rarely of interest to urbanism, becomes increasingly distant in the time of economic life — not the time of clocks or calendars —, increasingly distant and older and less effective than the part of the city that is necessary to the wealthy life of those large businesses.

Premature aging of the city, premature aging of urban objects. The so-called urban renewal, whatever its name might be, is at the same time an instrument of aging of the city as a whole. And one of

the results of this is the widening within the city of functional contrasts and value differences, whatever the meaning of word value, which in turn results in a race for renewal; in other words, the need to renovate presents itself in a much stronger and more urgent manner than before, increasing the possibility of an even more conflicting urban growth devoid of social control. "Speed" always brought with it differences, and in the cities these differences increase as the distance between the new and the old increases. And yet only the new is encouraged, only the new is favored. The most that is done for the old is to ask it to renew or adapt itself, which results in an evolution that is chaotic and even faster than before, compatible with the speed inherent to neoliberalism.

The differences and even the oppositions between the users of the new and the users of the old increase, which is equivalent to a veritable revolution of urban values: a widening of the differences between urban agents, firms, people, and institutions.

In the Third World... I prefer that expression to that of "peripheral country" — I will not subscribe to the absurdity of supposing that 5 billion people are peripheral in relationship to that small billion that makes up the so-called Western World. The Third World has experienced through this evolutionary framework a series of consequences that I will also briefly address: the first is that the city becomes a place where variety is greater and the levels of activity and wealth are more numerous. The second is that individual differences increase, including differences of opportunity.

There is also in the Third World a most important urban factor, which is the absence or precariousness of citizenship. Citizenship is a central datum in the understanding of urban directions. It is a central fact when trying to understand why such and such urban approach was taken. It is a measuring rod for the form in which cities may evolve. I insist on this because I believe that it is a subject that is not being sufficiently dealt with. It certainly is considered, but in a tangential manner, when it could be extremely useful in distinguishing urban forms and contents in regions such as the underdeveloped world and especially in regions such as Europe, where the notion of citizenship, albeit strongly eroded by neoliberal assaults, still persists.

And there is above all the escalation of the tendency of large cities to attract poor people, because the countryside is modernized and it drives away the poor, who migrate to the cities, the only places capable of providing activities for the poor, of storing the poor — the city as a warehouse for the poor —, of producing poor people — the city, through its organization, as capable of being a factory of

poor people. This is what under current circumstances makes every new brick a piece of the urban crisis, an engine of the urban crisis. The Urbanism of renewal creates more problems than it solves.

Within this context we need to ask ourselves what is the current role of large businesses and international banks on urban approaches and urban production. This is an extremely important piece of data: to investigate, on one hand, how international banks interfere in urban life, especially in larger cities of underdeveloped countries, but also to investigate how businesses, insofar as they locate themselves and impose a certain type of consumption of space, a certain functionality of space, demand that the government adapt itself to their needs, those of large businesses. A distortion that can be easily observed in Brazil, that of the territorial architecture of the nation as a whole, but also of each of its subsets, beginning with the city, resulting from the action of large businesses, which have their own spatial needs in the avid world of fluidity and in a world where production is increasingly dependent on the conditions offered by space.

Note how the issues for the city and for urbanism get complicated in this end of the 20th century for underdeveloped countries. Large businesses, large international banks. International banks choose the investments they want to make, pay the research studies that justify such ventures, publicize the ideas that encourage this type of renewal, and build both the new city and the new urban ideology. Large businesses interfere on urban renewal, but they also interfere on everyday urban reality. The cities are so large that the so-called rational solutions to its problems — energy, water, transportation, garbage, and services in general — are entrusted to those large businesses whose participation is suggested to city and national governments by the international banks in charge of “helping” solve the urban problems.

Note for example the various contracts signed by the IDB, not to mention the World Bank, with Brazilian and Latin American municipalities. This happens also because within each country — as we all know, Brazil is perhaps the best example of this — the legislative bodies — the Senate of the Republic, the House of Representatives — govern less than the Central Bank does. The Central Bank disposes, sets the conditions to respond rapidly to demands that are highly mutable within the short response time dictated by the interests of large international firms, and thus the nation is led in respect to that which is its most important. The legislation relevant to the reorganization of the territory and the city is thus driven, directly and indirectly, much more by the Central Bank, through decrees developed overnight, than by the Senate of the Republic and the House of Representatives, whose decisions are considered too slow.

I could not discuss the question of urbanism or even the urban question if I were to omit this fact, which is a new yet genuine fact of the history of the world and of the history of each place. This indicates that it is time to go back to the debate. It indicates that it is not enough to add words of indignation to outdated formulas. It indicates that we need to have the courage that only intellectuals are capable of; that is, the courage to forget, because without forgetting it is impossible to renew anything, especially ideas. Ideas are a product of forgetfulness. And this is the reason why academic institutions are often an impediment to the progress of ideas, because such institutions are for the most part intellectual places where repetition is preferred to innovation, where carbon paper has a more important role than discovery, where conciliation has a more decisive role than debate.

This debate should perhaps begin with that set of ideas inherited from the 19th century, which in universities is known by the name of Marxism. All of us know that Marxism was not created in terms of the territory, but we also know that the territory, through its realization, through what it is, through the way in which it is structured, through the way in which it evolves, is the best philosophical place to develop Marxist concepts, which have become indispensable given that only capitalism exists. The “death” of socialism — a death in quotes, of course —, the victory of capitalism, means, as we all know, the present or impending triumph of Marxism.

Now, what to do today with ideas such as the notions of general capital and particular capital? Particular capital leads us to consider the technical side of production. But it is the general capital that forces us to think of the political side of production, which is global. This means that when we think of either São Paulo or [for me] the most beautiful small city of the Brazilian interior, Birigüi (Ana Fernandes’ homeland), we take the world as our reference, the world in its workings. But this leads us to abstraction, which often bothers us, because we are asked for concrete solutions, as if that had never existed.

And the notion of value — use value and trade value —, so abundantly applied to urban studies, when today we know that trade value precedes use value in the current conditions of globalization and not the other way around... how do we learn it and even teach it?

And the notion of absolute and relative surplus value, which also demands a different interpretation? And all of this is related to the production of the city or, as was said in earlier times, to the production and reproduction of the city, because a good Marxist never used the word “production” without adding “reproduction,” even he did not know what

he was talking about. But it is related especially to the issue of depreciation of non-hegemonic capital and to the issue of depreciation of labor within the city, without which it is impossible to understand what the city is.

It is this new organic composition of the territory that causes technical or scientific informational work to have such an important role, and that shifts the focus from the secondary to the tertiary sector, a fact that we have difficulty accepting, especially in Brazil, because the country's hegemonic University of urban thought is located in a city that until recently was considered locomotive because it was the industrial capital, and it took 25 years to realize that it was no longer so, but that it continued to be locomotive because it was the relational capital of services.

I believe that the role of large businesses, of giant businesses, and the relationship they have with the government — or, rather, the non-government — are facts of the urban crisis that we sometimes approach with a purely instrumental vision, which is not nearly sufficient.

The ungovernableness of the cities we are experiencing goes hand in hand with the ungovernableness of countries. Latin America is a continent that is currently ungovernable, which points to the need to substitute the system of neoliberalism and globalization in its current form for something else.

The city is precisely the place that represents the change that society demands, since in it, in different ways, is taking place what economists like Montchrétien and William Petty suggested existed in their days, when they wrote that we should pay attention to the explosive political content of unjust cities. Unjust cities; in other words, cities where the citizen is not supreme.

In the Third World, and especially in Latin America, the city is the source of employment for most of the active population; the city is the means of subsistence for most people. All of this, I repeat, is what leads to a shift in the role of tertiaries, all tertiaries, the very new ones as well as banal or primitive ones, as revealers of the future.

But this also points to us, and our job is to think. It points to the fact that the city in this turn of the century is doubly critical. It is critical because of the life that is lived within it, but it is above all critical, and this should be our first concern, because of the fact that the city highlights the dysfunctions of the political and economic system in which we live. At the same time this presents itself as a warning, because the city becomes highly critical in a world that tends to be highly uncritical, a fact that widens the scope of our duty as thinkers of the city, of our duty in the idealization of the city of the future... and this

task is Herculean. I hope that urbanists will accept the help of other specialists in this task. Sometimes one gets the impression that they want no help. The Brazilian case seems to me exemplary of this near monopoly of thought and action on the city still held by urbanists. I think this is a pity, because it limits the possibility of a vision that goes beyond the vision of objects and things, which Rousseau already condemned, and assigns to actions a secondary or residual role.

Urbanism is the — sometimes — scientifically founded art of arranging things. But we need more than blind practice; we need a theory capable of uniting things and actions, in other words, capable of uniting technique and politics. And this is where the role of ideas comes in, of an urbanologic and not merely urbanistic imagination, without which there is no hope for thought on the city and will most likely be no hope for urban practice.

I suppose that given this proposal we need to beware of the danger of invalidating the debate. For example, as a result of a rejection of a notion of the future that is inconsistent with our vision of what is to come, but also as a result of seeking shelter in the dictionary.

An example can be found in the difference between the notion of landscape and the notion of space. Obviously, this legacy was handed down to us in part by geographers, by European geography, which during this entire century made the terrible mistake of assimilating the idea of space to the idea of landscape, which for geography and its parallel disciplines made it difficult to understand the process of action, attributing virtues to materiality that it cannot have. I believe it is now time to set into motion that urbanologic imagination, that jump from urbanism to urbanology, an urbanology of which urbanism will always be an important part. Today we find it difficult to do so because the other disciplines of the urban were somehow eclipsed by urbanism: urban geography was somehow eclipsed; urban sociology lost its vitality; urban anthropology reduced its field of action. And, on the contrary, there was, on one hand, an ascendancy of intellectual practices that give pure materiality the prerogative over action: studies on transportation, public spaces, etc.; and on the other, intellectual practices that are not committed to the importance of material reality: studies that imagine they can address the urban question solely through culture, ideas of identity, the imaginary. We need to go beyond the stage where we maintain a separate vision of processes, which are by nature a piece of the urban whole. This is not easy because we live a moment of history that is imbued with a strong feeling of urgency, resulting from a fast and bustling world

that discourages lengthy studies and all-encompassing practices, so that even progressive administrations fail to look for progressive solutions. It is no longer surprising to find municipalities headed by progressive mayors adopting neoliberal practices.

I believe it is urgent. I am sure that urbanists will make a formidable contribution because they are above all men and women who never lacked the imagination I advocate, allowing us to rapidly reach a citizen urbanism instead of an entrepreneurial urbanism; a citizen planning instead of a planning that interests and benefits only a part of the population.

Once again I would like to thank Frederico. I also reiterate my gratitude to the Organizing Commission for the great distinction of making me one of the speakers of this meeting.

KEYWORDS

globalization, third world, urbanism, citizenship.

Milton Santos (1926-2001), a geographer born in Bahia, was one of the internationally most known Brazilian intellectuals. Due his political ideas, he spent two months in a military prison in Salvador, Brazil. Released after the symptoms of a heart attack, he left for France in 1964. The forced exile projected him internationally. He became professor of the universities of Paris, Columbia, Toronto and Der Assalaam and lived in Venezuela and United Kingdom. He returned to Brazil in 1977. Doctor in Geography for the University of Estrasburgo and honoris causa doctor for various Universities in Brazil, Italy and France, he became professor of the Federal University of Bahia, visiting professor in Stanford and titular professor of the Geography Department of the São Paulo University and member of the National Advice of Human Development, Brazil. For a long time, he has been UN, OEA, UNESCO and OIT adviser, whose Committee for the Study of the Urbanization and the Work he has been the manager. He was the only scholar outside the Anglo-Saxon world to receive what could be considered the Nobel Prize for Geography, the Vautrin Lud prize in 1994. Milton Santos searched to free geography of its isolation, adding to it contributions from economy, sociology and philosophy. He has published more than 40 books and 300 articles. His more important works are: "The Center of the City of Salvador" (1959), "The City in the Underdeveloped Countries" (1965), "The Divided Space" (1978), "Space and Society" (1979), "Space and Method" (1985), "The Brazilian Urbanization" (1993), "For an other Globalization" (2000). Besides ten of medals, he had been awarded with the following prizes: "Technological Merit" in 1997 (Union of the Engineers of the State of São Paulo),

Personality of the Year of 1997 (Institute of the Architects of Brazil), and the Jabuti Prize of 1997, for the book "The Nature of the Space, Technique and Time, Reason and Emotion".